

CODEBOOK REINCLU GEN

**RETHINKING INCLUSION AND GENDER EMPOWERMENT:
A PARTICIPATORY ACTION RESEARCH**

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We present the codebook that we used to analyse the data collected during the qualitative research of the ReIncluGen project. More information can be found at: www.reincludgen.be. This codebook includes the codes and the explanation given per code. Alongside, socio-demographic data was collected and memos were written.

We divided it into two main coding trees:

Codetree CSO staff

1. **Definitions of gender empowerment “in theory” by CSOs under study:** Explicit or implicit definitions in CSO’s documents available (websites, mission statements, general program, etc). Different spheres (social; social-educative; economic; cultural...). When the concept appears, is it in a unidimensional and generic way or multidimensional and specified way? Explicit narrative of CSO origin/history from the staff and relation to gender perspective and empowerment. It can be relevant in cases where for instance the CSO has been funded by a leader who took a specific perspective which permeates their approach, but different scenarios can have had an impact on their views, practices.
2. **Definitions of empowerment “in practice”:** Practices and activities in CSOs linked to the objectives of gender empowerment (gender emancipation or other concepts related to transforming unequal social structures).
3. **Other relevant concepts and perspectives that come up during the interviews with the CSOs**
 - a. **Gender**
 - b. **Migration and diversity**
4. **Internal strengths and weaknesses** identified by staff in achieving gender empowerment and inclusion through their CSO
5. **External threats** and opportunities identified by staff in achieving inclusion through their CSO
6. **Link between empowerment and inclusion in CSOs:** Reflect on whether you have found a link between empowerment and inclusion in the discourses or in the practices. Relevant connections, any gaps, silences, contradictions...

Codetree CSO participants

1. **Women’s definitions of gender empowerment:** This may include explicit definitions referred by woman or reflections on related concepts (power, position and participation in different spheres, control of resources, agency capacity, authority, decision-making capacity, among others), taking into the account:
 - Awareness of status in the social structure or social locations (current and life course: stages)

- In social relations at different social spheres (egalitarian/ domination, subordination... in comparison to other women's groups, to men).
 - In relation to different institutions (egalitarian/ exclusion, discrimination)
 - Awareness of citizenship rights (beliefs about their rights and capabilities.)
 - Processes of change / transformation of subordinate structures (individual and/or collective) that impact on greater decision-making capacity, participation, access to resources and a perception of agency.
2. **Women's experiences of gender empowerment in their everyday lives:**
 - **Type of participation in different social spheres** (equal conditions? decision-making capacity? accountability: situation of inclusion/exclusion)
 - Economic dimension (economic autonomy and welfare, control of resources in public/private domain, work situation and skills, dedication to care work, career issues, educational processes (formal and non-formal), aspirations and expectations...)
 - Social dimension (type of social relationships, perceived pressure on gender mandates (intra-community/ in the host society), bargaining power on issues such as number of children, partner choice, children's education/care, friendship, issues related to gender-based violence, among others)
 - Socio-cultural (cultural participation and networking activities)
 - Political dimension (political participation and citizenship rights)
 3. **Preconditions to realise processes of empowerment:** Reflections linked to conditions of emancipation experienced by women in society
 4. **Access/ barriers to participation** they have encountered: in the social context in different spheres (social relations/institutions) and in the life course (different moments/ stages of life).
 5. **Perceived CSO practices to support gender empowerment:** Practices valued by women (awareness, access to resources and participation or capacity to transform situations of subordination, exclusion, or discrimination.)
 6. **Unmet needs and rights by CSOs:**
 - Social problems identified as relevant from their perspectives.
 - Needs in different social spheres.
 - Limitations on the exercise of rights